

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SARKADY****FIRST NAME: EMESE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on macOS Sonoma 14.5

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What should NOT be included in the conclusion chapter of a dissertation?

- Restate your answer to the question.
- Re-summarize the main points.
- Offer exposition and evidence to develop your argument.¹**
- Include a final, broad statement (about possible implications, future directions for research, to qualify the conclusion, etc.).

2. Which sentence is punctuated incorrectly?

- I would like to be slim: I will try to lose weight.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 10.

- We were in trouble this time: we had never been in trouble before.**²
- A new drink was introduced to Britain: tea.
- We were in trouble this time: the lid has come off.
3. Which of the four purposes should tertiary sources be used in research?
- To keep up with current research.
- To find models for your own research and analysis.
- To find other points of view.
- To get a broad overview of your topic.**³
4. Which is the correct order to build a research argument?
- Claim-evidence-reason-acknowledgment/response-warrant.
- Reason-claim-warrant-evidence-acknowledgment/response.
- Claim-evidence-reason-warrant-acknowledgment/response.
- Claim-reason-evidence-acknowledgment/reason.**⁴
5. Which should NOT be done when labelling a table?
- Do not use noun phrases; avoid participles in favour of relative clauses.**⁵
- Avoid making the title or caption a general topic.

² Ibid., 18.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 37.

⁴ Ibid., 58

⁵ Ibid., 88.

- Do not give background information or characterize what the data imply.
 - Be sure labels distinguish graphics presenting similar data.
6. In what order should the four research documents be written?
- Manuscript-prospectus-concept paper-dissertation.
 - Concept paper-prospectus-dissertation-manuscript.
 - Prospectus-concept paper-dissertation-manuscript.
 - Concept paper-prospectus-dissertation-manuscript.**⁶
7. Which type of bias does the following definition fit: It ‘results from the perceived efficacy of specific constructs used to conceptualize human development, personality, and service delivery interventions’?
- Intervention.
 - Policy.
 - Theory.**⁷
 - Experience.
8. Which of the following measures does not belong to the types of qualitative research?
- Focus group.
 - Tests.**⁸

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

⁷ Ibid., 8

⁸ Ibid., 37

- Observations using unobtrusive or participant observations.
- Questionnaires using predominantly open-ended items.

9. Which name is correctly used by the relevant institution in documents for external audiences?

- World Health Organisation.
- WHO headquarters.**⁹
- the WHO.
- WHO regional offices.

10. Which term would be incorrectly spelt in WHO documents?

- Oestrogen.**¹⁰
- Estrus.
- Oesophagus.
- Oedema.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 3.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 13

WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.